

PSYCHOLOGICAL AND PEDAGOGICAL FOUNDATIONS OF HEALTH-PRESERVING KNOWLEDGE FOR FUTURE TEACHERS

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Abstract. *This article examines the theoretical and practical aspects of forming health-preserving knowledge in future educators. It covers health-preserving knowledge, psychological-pedagogical foundations, active learning methods, and innovative technologies. Methodological recommendations for developing health-preserving competence are provided.*

Keywords: *health preservation, pedagogical competence, psychological-pedagogical foundations, innovative educational technologies, health-preserving knowledge.*

Modern education imposes increased requirements on the professional training of future teachers, especially in terms of developing their knowledge and competencies that contribute to the preservation of students' health. The development of health-preserving knowledge among future teachers is a crucial component of their professional competence, as pedagogical activity directly affects the physical and mental well-being of students.

The formation of this competence requires a comprehensive approach, including the study of the psychological and pedagogical foundations of health preservation, active learning methods, and the implementation of innovative educational technologies. An important aspect is the development of scientifically grounded methodological recommendations aimed at integrating health-preserving technologies into the educational process.

This paper examines the theoretical and practical aspects of developing health-preserving knowledge among future teachers, analyzes modern approaches to its development, and proposes ways to enhance the effectiveness of the educational process in this area.

It should be noted that one of the priority tasks of the modern education system is the preservation and strengthening of students' health, the formation of health values and philosophy, the promotion of a healthy lifestyle, and the development of health culture. Deviations in students' moral and physical health are caused by modern stressors, social, environmental, and psychological pressures.

The health status of the younger generation is a key indicator of societal and state well-being, reflecting not only the current situation but also providing a forecast for the future. The country's workforce, its security, political stability, economic prosperity, and the moral and ethical level of the population are directly related to the health of young people [1]. In recent years, attention to health issues in our country has significantly increased, leading to a greater focus on the health of schoolchildren, lyceum, and college students. The challenges in this area have been known and discussed for a long time, but today the problem has become particularly urgent [2].

Over the past decade, the number of factors that previously did not pose significant problems for doctors, teachers, and parents has increased. Academic workloads continue to grow year by year, while leisure time is increasingly spent watching videos and playing computer games, leading to physical inactivity, poor posture, and vision problems [3]. The effort to address the

health preservation issues of educational process participants and to instill a culture of a healthy lifestyle relies on the support of parents, the state healthcare system, and public organizations [4].

In the given context, health-preserving activities (HPA) are an expression of human activity, driven by specific conscious motives and aimed at achieving certain goals. Social-normative competence in health-preserving activities can also be considered as a student's level of readiness for the practical application of health-preserving methods and tools. This includes knowledge, skills, and professional-personal qualities relevant to their future professional activities.

Currently, Uzbekistan's policy on protecting the health of the younger generation includes a range of initiatives and programs aimed at ensuring students' health and well-being. The country implements educational programs on disease prevention, vaccination, compliance with sanitary and epidemiological regulations, medical examinations, and consultations. Additionally, several health-improving programs are being carried out to enhance public knowledge about health preservation [5].

An equally important aspect is educating the population about a healthy lifestyle, proper nutrition, physical activity, and disease prevention. The state also supports the development of children's medical institutions, ensuring access to quality healthcare services for the younger generation [4].

Overall, social policy in the field of healthcare for the younger generation in Uzbekistan is aimed at creating conditions for the healthy development of children and youth, as well as improving the quality of life of the population [1].

At the same time, social policy in Uzbekistan regarding the promotion of health-preserving knowledge among the younger generation includes a number of initiatives and programs aimed at increasing teachers' awareness of ensuring students' health and well-being. In particular, this knowledge relates to the provision of medical services. The state ensures the accessibility of medical services for students, including free preventive check-ups, vaccinations, disease treatment, and rehabilitation. Preventive measures are also implemented to address the most common childhood diseases, including the promotion of a healthy lifestyle, proper nutrition, physical activity, and hygiene. Additionally, health-preserving education is being introduced into school curricula through integrated lessons on a healthy lifestyle, sexual education [5], drug addiction prevention, and other aspects of health.

Alongside this, the country has established the "Mahalla and Family" Institute, which is designed to provide targeted and systematic support to families. This includes social support for families with children, such as financial assistance, health-preserving specialist consultations, and parental support programs. Health-preserving psychological assistance is also gaining importance, ensuring the availability of psychological help for both students and educators, including counseling and support for psychological issues.

Special attention is given to creating a safe environment, which includes efforts to establish a health-preserving environment for the younger generation, as well as measures to combat child labor, violence, and other threats and dangers.

In general, social policy aimed at increasing health-preserving knowledge among the younger generation and educators in Uzbekistan seeks to ensure the full physical, psychological, and social development of children and adolescents, as well as to promote healthy habits and lifestyles among youth.

In the National Concepts for the Development of Healthcare and Education until 2030, one of the priorities is the health of students, as its effective resolution will ensure the quality of education and the ability of future citizens of Uzbekistan to fulfill their social functions. It is well known that the health of modern students requires special attention due to the increasing share of chronic diseases in the overall morbidity structure. Harmful habits, such as the use of electronic cigarettes and various forms of "mania," including gaming addiction, gadget addiction, television addiction, and others [6], have a significant negative impact on students' health.

In the concept of developing the higher education system, it is emphasized that university teachers, together with medical professionals, psychologists, and the public, need to organize educational activities in such a way that students improve their health, graduate from university in good health, and continue to strengthen it throughout their lives. To implement health-preserving activities, educators must have a clear understanding of the essence of health and a healthy lifestyle, which have become fundamental concepts in modern education.

The concept of "health-preserving technologies," introduced in recent years, involves the consolidation of efforts by educational institutions aimed at maintaining, shaping, and strengthening the health of students. These technologies address the task of preserving and improving the health of today's students, enabling them to raise and educate their own children in a healthy way in the future.

In Russian universities, a course called "Health-Preserving Technologies in Professional and Pedagogical Education" has been introduced. Its goal is to shape the professional consciousness of future bachelor-level vocational educators by providing them with a comprehensive set of theoretical knowledge about health-preserving technologies in professional and pedagogical education. Additionally, the course aims to develop professional skills that enable future vocational education bachelors to apply their knowledge in preserving and strengthening the health of participants in the educational process [7].

Modern education imposes increased requirements on the professional training of future teachers, particularly in terms of developing their knowledge and competencies that contribute to maintaining students' health. The development of health-preserving knowledge among future teachers is a crucial component of their professional competence, as teaching activities directly impact the physical and mental well-being of students.

The formation of this competence requires a comprehensive approach, including the study of psychological and pedagogical foundations of health preservation, active learning methods, and the implementation of innovative educational technologies. An important aspect is the development of scientifically grounded methodological recommendations aimed at integrating health-preserving technologies into the educational process.

This paper examines the theoretical and practical aspects of developing health-preserving knowledge among future teachers, analyzes modern approaches to their development, and proposes ways to improve the effectiveness of the educational process in this field.

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